

Data Haptification as Feedback for Haptic Interactions - Multi-Parameter Monitoring during Planning Tasks

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Abstract. Some manual input tasks on computer are complex or demanding enough to deserve a non-standard, maybe even custom, input device. These devices are usually utilized to deliver the best economics, the best precision and the most rich interactions. However, when tasks are complex enough to necessitate special devices, their outcomes will often also be complex enough that it can be unclear whether the input actually achieved the desired goal. An example for this are CAD-driven planning tasks, in which an input device might allow for easy modelling of certain situations, but the effects of these planning decisions will not become clear until later analysis or review. In this paper, we propose a type of input system in which an input device makes use of immediate vibrotactile and force feedback to inform the user about the effects of their inputs. The feedback a device can offer is thus not only used for making it easier to use, but for data haptification.

Keywords: Haptification · Human-Computer Interaction · Urban Planning.

1 Introduction

Interaction devices are often capable of playing vibrotactile or even kinesthetic feedback. This feedback usually communicates simple information, like warning about an error or acknowledging which type of interaction was triggered. In certain contexts however, like CAD modelling for planning tasks, the effects of an interaction can be far more complex. Moving a virtual beam is a simple interaction, but the effects can reach far into other stages of planning, like structural soundness or the routing of energy or water. In such cases, we could utilize direct feedback to communicate information about the outcomes of an interaction. Displaying data as haptic feedback is referred to as *Haptification*, or the use of *Tactile Icons* [2], but so far has not been widely applied to this type of complex multi-parameter scenario. In this paper, we will thus first discuss a conceptual basis for using haptification as data-driven feedback for interactions, and then apply these concepts to a planning tasks from the field of street planning.

2 Interaction Feedback Haptifications

In visualization, we encode data into visual variables according to certain mapping rules. The variables available to us in haptification have similarly been discussed in many different contexts in the literature. There are variables for static and tangible objects, like 3d-printed data physicalizations, or variables for more dynamic devices,

like VR controllers or force-feedback systems [4]. They can pertain directly to haptic phenomena, like vibrations, movements or the weight of tangible objects, or be second-order effects of these phenomena, like other variables changing over time. Adopting a classification from Berger [1], we distinguish variables into the following types:

Tactile: Variables that are felt on the users skin, like vibration intensity or temperature

Kinesthetic: Variables that enact force against the user, like movement, resistance, drag

Physical: Variables that represent physical changes in the device, like orientation, size, shape, weight distribution, material properties, surface properties

Temporal: Variables that describe the occurrence of other variables, like duration, display date, rate of change, order, frequency, synchronization, composition

To create haptified feedback, we have to establish how these variable types can be linked to (a) certain types of interaction and (b) certain types of data values influenced by that interaction. Gonzalez-Franco et al. [3] present a classification of hand-object interactions, from which four types are relevant for our use case. For the purposes of variable mapping, values will fall into three classes: nominal, ordinal or numerical. How these aspects relate to each other is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The feedback loop implemented by interaction feedback haptifications. Lines show which value types can be displayed by which kind of variable and which variable types can be feedback for which interactions. Dotted lines show that a mapping is possible, but not always ideal.

Use Case: A Haptic Knob for Street Planning

When a street is planned, the width of different parts of the street (e.g. road, bike lane, sidewalk) is defined through sectional views defined along an axis. A crucial question during this process is what the ideal space allotted to each section is. Usually, a first draft that follows all necessary rules and regulations (e.g. a bike lane has to be wide enough to safely bike alongside cars) is created. This can be a very lengthy process, as all segments compete with each other for space. With an interaction device that immediately offers haptic feedback about the consequences of a certain change in width, this process can be much more immediate, preventing misinformed decision at the time of drawing.

A fitting interaction device for such a road planning task would be a haptic knob that can be twisted left and right to increase or decrease the width of segments, paired with a set of keys to change the active segment. Parameters to haptify here would be compound measures like bikeability, walkability, driveability, or the street microclimate. These values have to be approximated in real-time in order to act as immediate feedback.

Variables offered by a haptic knob include vibration intensity, resistance points to overcome, continuous drag against movements, as well as self-movement of the knob. There are many considerations when selecting variables. For example, the microclimate likely is represented by a set of ordinal classes ranging from perfect to bad conditions, and can thus be represented by discrete resistance points during the rotation. Each click that happens when the user overcomes the resistance represents the shift into a new class. The three traffic values are usually numerical and thus require other variables. Given this, a possible design for the full system is shown in Figure 2. The final design would also need to consider the cognitive load of several simultaneous haptifications.

Fig. 2. An interaction changes the width of one part of a street section (blue arrows), causing several metrics to be computed and played back as a haptification. Forces that can be overcome are shown by dotted lines, the purple line shows a limit to which the knob will always snap back.

3 Outlook

In a next step, a user study is needed to answer questions about whether users can distinguish all five variables during interactions, and about which variables are most effective for mapping which type of value. For a practical application, the system should also be expanded to allow quick movement up and down the planning axis, to be able to define whole streets instead of just individual sections. Other possible use cases for such feedback haptifications include complex steering and navigation tasks.

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